

Cardiac Involvement in Systemic Lupus Erythematosus Seen in Antananarivo Madagascar

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is an autoimmune disease of unknown etiology that can cause a variety of organ damage, including cardiac involvement. The aim of this study is to describe the epidemiological and clinical profiles of lupus patients with cardiac involvement.

Methods: This is a 7-year retrospective descriptive study (January 2015 to December 2021) including lupus patients with cardiac involvement, diagnosed by cardiac Doppler ultrasound and ECG, hospitalized in the JRB and CENHOSOA teaching hospitals.

Results: Twenty-one patients were included, with a mean age of 31.31 years (± 14.40) and a sex ratio (M/F) of 0.1. Dyspnea (n=6) and edema (n=8) were the main clinical manifestations. Antinuclear and anti-native DNA antibodies

were positive in 15 (71.4%) and 13 (61.9%) patients respectively. ECG was abnormal in 13 patients (61.9%). Pericardial effusion (71.4%), impaired left ventricular ejection fraction (42.9%), valvulopathy (42.9%) and pulmonary hypertension (33.3%) were the most common cardiac Doppler ultrasound abnormalities. Pericarditis was diagnosed in 13 patients (61.8%) and myocarditis in 6 (28.8%). Treatment was based on corticosteroid therapy (18 or 85.7%), hydroxychloroquine (14 or 66.7%), and immunosuppressor (4 or 19.1%). Four patients (19.1%) died.

Conclusion: Cardiac involvement is prognostic in lupus patients and should be systematically investigated.

Keywords: Cardiac Damage; Systemic Lupus Erythematosus; Epidemiological Profile

INTRODUCTION

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a non-organ-specific autoimmune disease that can affect the heart. Its prevalence in the general population is estimated at 41 cases per 100,000 inhabitants, varying by ethnic group. It affects all populations and races, with a large predominance in women of childbearing age, and a female/male sex ratio of 9 before the menopause. The Caucasian race is particularly affected, with a higher clinical severity [1]. Cardiac involvement in SLE is present in 25 to 82% of cases, and represents one of the greatest causes of morbidity and mortality in the disease, despite the rarity of clinical signs [2, 3, 4]. In addition to traditional risk factors, SLE itself constitutes a cardiovascular risk factor for lupus patients [3, 5, 6]. Cardiac involvement may be discovered during the course of the disease, but may also be indicative of lupus disease [6, 7, 8]. It can affect all three tunics of the heart: the pericardium, for pericarditis; the myocardium, for myocarditis; and the endocardium, for endocarditis [2, 9, 10]. Several authors report that electrocardiograms and cardiac Doppler ultrasound are the most accessible and non-invasive means of investigating these conditions [11, 12, 13]. In the face of numerous studies of SLE in Madagascar, studies of cardiac involvement in the disease remain limited and few in number. The aims of this study are to describe the epidemiological, clinical, paraclinical and evolutionary aspects of cardiac involvement in SLE, based on cases observed in the Centre Hospitalier Soavinandriana and Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Joseph Raseta Befelatanana, in order to distinguish lupus involvement behind these often unspecific manifestations, and thus facilitate appropriate and effective management; but also to draw the attention of physicians to the cardiac aspects of SLE.

METHODOLOGY

This retrospective, descriptive study was carried out in two of Madagascar's major hospitals based in Antananarivo: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Joseph Raseta Befelatanana (CHU-JRB) and Centre Hospitalier de Soavinandriana (CENHOSOA). Both hospitals have internal medicine departments staffed by specialists in internal medicine and cardiovascular disease, who are able to treat patients with systemic diseases such as lupus. Data for the present study covered a 7-year period from January 01, 2015 to December 31, 2021. The study population included all patients hospitalized for SLE who met the ACR 1997 criteria. All hospitalized lupus patients with cardiac involvement were included. The diagnosis of cardiac involvement in lupus patients was made by cardiac Doppler ultrasound. Epidemiological, clinical, therapeutic and evolutionary data were studied. Data were entered and processed using Excel® 2010. For epidemiological parameters, age, gender and work sector were studied. For clinical parameters, the existence or absence of personal medical history such as arterial hypertension, diabetes and asthma, the toxic habits

of patients, i.e. smoking, ethylism and decoction intake, as well as the presence of autoimmune disease, notably lupus, in the family were studied. With regard to symptomatology, cardiovascular clinical signs such as chest pain, dyspnea, edema of the lower limbs, palpitations and syncope were mentioned. The chronology of the discovery of cardiac involvement in relation to the diagnosis of SLE was also described. Biological parameters included the presence or absence of inflammatory syndrome, as measured by sedimentation rate and CRP, hematological disorders such as anemia, leukopenia and thrombocytopenia, and positive immunological tests, notably anti-nuclear antibody, anti-native DNA and anti-soluble polynuclear antigen. For ultrasound parameters, the diagnosis of cardiac involvement (pericarditis, myocarditis, endocarditis), left ventricular systolic function (left ventricular ejection fraction), the presence of pericardial effusion complicated by tamponade or not, segmental kinetic disorder, valvulopathy, pulmonary hypertension and vegetation were studied. Concerning the limits of the study, the diagnosis of lupus heart disease was based on clinical, biological and echocardiographic arguments available in the patients' files. Other examinations such as cardiac magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and/or coronary angiography are recommended to rule out possible differential diagnoses.

RESULTS

During the study period, twenty-one lupus patients met the inclusion criteria out of 180 identified lupus cases. The prevalence of cardiac involvement in lupus patients was 11.6% over a 7-year period, or 1.6% in one year. The mean age was 31.33 years, with a standard deviation of 14.40 years and extremes of 9 and 63 years. The majority of patients (61.2%) were aged between 21 and 30. Nineteen of these patients were women (90.47%) and two men, with a sex ratio of 0.1. The majority of patients were students with a proportion of 38.1%; workers in the secondary sectors accounted for 23.8% and those in the tertiary sectors for 23.8%. Eighty-one percent (n=17) of patients were from Antananarivo, two (9.5%) from Fianarantsoa and two (9.5%) from Toamasina. According to medical history, six patients (28.6%) were hypertensive; one patient (4.8%) had a history of asthma associated with diabetes and hypertension. The majority (66.6%) of patients had no particular medical history. As for toxic habits, 3 patients (14.3%) were alcoholics, one (4.8%) was a smoker and one (4.8%) took herbal tea. Lupus was identified in the family of 3 patients (14.3%) (Table 1). In patients with lupus, dyspnea was present in 6 (28.6%), syncope in 2 (9.5%), chest pain and palpitations in 1 (4.7%). Dyspnea associated with edema of the lower limbs was reported in 8 patients (38.1%). Three patients (14.2%) were asymptomatic. (Table 2). Pericardial effusion was found in 15 patients (71.4%), depending on the ultrasound abnormality. Impaired LV systolic function was found in 9 patients (42.9%). Hypokinesia was observed in 28.6% of cases (6). Valvulopathy was observed in 9 lupus patients (42.9%). Pulmonary hypertension (PAH) and pericardial tamponade were reported in 7 (33.3%) and 3 (14.3%) patients respectively (Table 4). Concerning the chronology of cardiac involvement and the diagnosis of lupus, cardiac involvement appeared during the course of lupus in 9 patients (42.61%). In 28.57% of cases (n = 6), it was revelatory of the disease leading to the diagnosis. And in 5 patients (23.8%), cardiac involvement was present long before the diagnosis of SLE was made. Cardiac involvement occurred during a lupus relapse in 6 patients (28.57%), and was discovered during remission in 4 patients (19.04%). For the diagnosis of cardiac involvement, lupus pericarditis was selected in 13 patients (61.9%) and myocarditis in 6 (28.5%) (Table 2). Biologically, 20 patients (95.3%) showed an inflammatory syndrome. Anemia

and leukopenia were observed in 13 (61.9%) and 5 (23.8%) patients respectively. Antinuclear antibody testing was performed in 16 lupus patients (76.19%), and was positive in 15 (71.4%); anti-native DNA antibody testing was performed in 14 (66.66%), and was present in 13 (61.9%). Antiphospholipid antibodies were positive in 3 patients (14.3%). Anti-U1 RNP, anti-SSA and anti-SSB were positive in 4 (19.1%), 4 (19.1%) and 7 (33.3%) patients respectively. (Table 3). As for treatment, 18 patients (85.7%) received corticosteroids, 14 (66.7%) hydroxychloroquine and 4 (19.1%) immunosuppressants. Pericardial drainage was performed in 4 patients (19.1%) and one patient (4.8%) underwent valve replacement. (Table 5). As for hospitalization, death occurred in 4 patients (19.1%). Of the 13 cases of pericarditis, 3 required pericardial drainage, and all died. The 6 cases of myocarditis evolved favorably on corticosteroids, 2 of which required immunosuppressive therapy. In the two cases of Libman Sacks endocarditis, one was complicated by an oslerian superinfection, with a favourable outcome under appropriate treatment, while the other case, which had benefited from mechanical valve replacement, died as a result of Covid-19.

Table 1: Patient characteristics by age, profession and previous history.

Parameters	n=21 (%)
Age (years)	
≤ 20 years	6/21 (28,6)
[21-35]	6/21 (28,6)
[36-50]	7/21 (33,3)
≥ 50 years	2/21 (9,5)
Female	19/21 (90,5)
Male	2/21 (9,5)
Student	8/21 (38,1)
Unemployed	2/21 (9,5)
Primary sector	1/21 (4,7)
Secondary sector	5/21 (23,8)
Tertiary sector	5/21 (23,8)
History	
HBP	6/21 (28,6)
Asthma+ Diabetes+ HBP	1/21 (4,7)
Allergy	
Drugs (penicillin)	3/21 (14,3)
Food	1/21 (4,7)
Smoking	1/21 (4,7)
Ethyl	3/21 (14,3)
Decoction intake	1/21 (4,7)
Lupus in family	3/21 (14,3)

Table 2: Clinical presentations and cardiac involvement.

Parameters	n = 21 (%)
Symptoms	
Chest pain	1/21 (4,7)
Dyspnea	6/21 (28,6)
Dyspnea + edema	8/21 (38,1)
Palpitation	1/21 (4,7)
Syncope	2/21 (9,5)
None	3/21 (14,2)
Cardiac involvement	
Pericarditis	13/21 (61,9)
Myocarditis	4/21 (19,0)
Endocarditis Libman Sack + Pericarditis	1/21 (4,7)
Myocarditis + Pericarditis	2/21 (9,5)
Oslerian endocarditis	1/21 (4,7)

Table 3: Patients' biological characteristics.

Parameters	n = 21 (%)
Elevated ESR, CRP	20/21 (95,3)
Anemia	13/21 (61,9)
Leukopenia	5/21 (23,8)
Antinuclear antibody	
Positive	15/21 (71,4)
Negative	1/21 (4,7)
Not done	5/21 (23,8)
Native anti-DNA	
Positive	13/21 (61,9)
Negative	1/21 (4,7)
Not done	7/21 (33,3)
Anti-phospholipid	
Positive	3/21 (14,3)
Negative	1/21 (4,7)
Not done	17/21 (80,9)
Anti-SSA/Ro	
Positive	4/21 (19,1)
Negative	5/21 (23,8)
Not done	12/21 (57,1)
Anti-SSB	
Positive	4/21 (19,1)
Negative	5/21 (23,8)
Not done	12/21 (57,1)
U1RNP	
Positive	7/21 (33,3)
Negative	2/21 (9,5)
Not done	12/21 (57,1)

Table 4: Trans-thoracic ultrasound characteristics.

Parameters	n = 21 (%)
Pericardial effusion	15/21 (71,4)
Impaired LVEF	9/21 (42,9)
Hypokinesia	6/21 (28,6)
Valvular vegetation	1/21 (4,7)
Mitral valve disease	9/21 (42,9)
PAH	7/21 (33,3)
Pericardial tamponade	3/21 (14,3)

Table 5: Patient profile according to specific lupus treatment received.

Treatments	n = 21 (%)
Drug	
Hydroxychloroquine	14/21 (66,6)
Corticosteroid therapy	18/21 (85,7)
Immunosuppressants	4/21 (19,1)
Surgery	
Pericardial drainage	4/21 (19,1)
Mechanical valve insertion	1/21 (4,7)

DISCUSSION

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic autoimmune disease of unknown etiology that can cause a variety of organ disorders. Cardiac involvement must be systematically detected, as it can be life-threatening. The aim of this study was to identify the clinical, paraclinical and therapeutic features of cardiac involvement in patients with SLE. The present study identified 180 cases of lupus, of which 21 patients had cardiac involvement. The prevalence of cardiac involvement in lupus patients was 11.6% over a 7-year period, i.e. a prevalence of 1.6% in one year in the CHU JRB and CENHOSOA. In Tunisia, Ghriss et al, in 2019 in an internal medicine department over a 17-year period following lupus patients found a frequency of cardiac involvement of 40.6% [14]. Ben Achour's 2018 study in the internal medicine department of the Tunis Military Hospital, over a 7-year period, found a 52.50% prevalence of cardiac involvement in lupus patients [15]. In Morocco, Bouatba et al. in 2014 in the internal medicine department of CHU Ibn Sina de Rabata reported a frequency of lupus cardiac involvement of 30.4% [16]. Harouna et al. in 2016 found that 31 patients among 212 cases of systemic lupus erythematosus presented with cardiac involvement, a prevalence of 14.62% [17]. A study conducted by Ngaidé et al in the Dakar region of Senegal in 2016 over a 1-year period found a frequency of cardiovascular manifestations of 46% [18]. This discrepancy in frequency could be explained by the difference in study populations and recruitment methods for each country. In this study, lupus patients are not routinely screened for cardiac involvement, which could influence this low prevalence compared with other studies. The main cardiac warning signs in the present study were dominated by the combination of dyspnea and generalized edema (38.1%). Dyspnea alone accounted for 28.6%. Other authors such as Ghriss et al. report chest pain and dyspnoea [14]. Ben Achour et al. in 2018, suggested that symptoms were dominated by objectified chest pain [15]. Harouna et al found that manifestations occurred in a context of initial pathology with an unobtrusive clinical picture dominated by dyspnea found in 12.9% and chest pain in 9.7% [17]. Dyspnea was also the most common symptomatology (26%), followed by palpitation (22%) in the study conducted by Ngaidé et al in Dakar [18]. Most

cases of cardiac involvement in lupus are of little or no symptomatology. Despite this, dyspnoea, chest pain, palpitations and oedema are the most commonly reported in several studies. Clinicians should therefore not rule out the diagnosis of lupus cardiac involvement in the face of these symptoms if the etiologies are not found. In this study, pericarditis was the main form of cardiac involvement in lupus patients, accounting for 61.9%, including 3 cases of tamponade. Myocarditis accounted for 28.5%. Some studies have also found more or less the same results. Ghriss et al. reported that pericarditis was the most frequent cardiac condition, accounting for 64.1% of cases, followed by valvulopathy (56.4%), myocarditis (7.7%) and endocarditis (2.6%) [14]. In Dakar, Ngaidé et al. found pericarditis in 54% of cases, including 2 cases of tamponade (5.6%), pulmonary hypertension in 22% and dilated cardiomyopathy in 9% of cases [18]. Ben Achour et al. found pericarditis in 23 patients (55%), with only one case of tamponade. Endocarditis and lupus myocarditis were found in one case each [15]. In Morocco, the study carried out by Bouatba et al. in 2014 in the internal medicine department of CHU Ibn Sina in Rabat found that pericarditis accounted for 73.1% of cases and myocarditis for 10.4% [16]. A study carried out at Tunis hospital by Hajji et al. found that pericarditis was present in 32.7% of lupus patients [19]. In Tunisia, Izidbih and his team found in their study that lupus affected all three tunics of the heart, with pericarditis predilection in 14.6% of cases [20]. Bestaoui et al found in their study that pericarditis was the most common cardiac condition, affecting 20% of patients, followed by pulmonary hypertension in 4.7% [21]. Ultrasound findings: pericardial effusion predominated, followed by impaired LV systolic function and hypokinesia. Valvular disease was present in 42.9% of patients. PAH and tamponade were visualized in 33.3% and 14.3% of patients respectively. Ghriss et al found that mitral insufficiency was present in 15.6% of patients, aortic insufficiency in 5.1% and tricuspid insufficiency in 2.1% [14]. Ben Achour et al. also found PAH in 16 patients (38%) and valvulopathy in 22 (52%). Cardiomegaly was observed in 9 patients (21%) [15]. Harouna et al. echocardiography confirmed 12.9% myocarditis, 6.5% Libman-Sacks endocarditis, 9.7% severe PAH constituting elements of severity and 87.1% pericarditis of small abundance constituting an element of benignity [17]. Routine cardiac ultrasound for lupus patients could be a practical, non-invasive means of screening and monitoring cardiac damage in these patients. Cardiac involvement in the present study was revelatory of lupus disease in 28.3% of cases, and in 47.6% of cases after diagnosis of the disease, 19% of which occurred outside the relapse. On the other hand, 23.8% of cardiac attacks were already present before the diagnosis of lupus and did not reveal the disease. Some authors, such as Maharaj et al., report the case of a 10-year-old girl presenting with a pericardial tamponade revealing lupus disease [7]. Larson and his team also described the case of an 18-year-old man diagnosed with pericarditis at the stage of tamponade revealing lupus [8]. Another case was reported by Umer et al. concerning an 11-year-old girl who presented with chest pain and dyspnoea. She was diagnosed with lupus-induced pericarditis on investigation [22]. Delayed diagnosis and lack of access to investigations to confirm the diagnosis of lupus could explain the diagnosis of cardiac involvement prior to lupus, especially in the uncomplicated stage. In practice, hospital practitioners should always consider lupus when faced with unexplained cardiac involvement, especially pericarditis in the tamponade stage. For treatment, the majority of patients received hydroxychloroquine and corticosteroid therapy, and only 19.1% immunosuppressive therapy. Three cases required emergency pericardial drainage because of the major risk of tamponade. Ghriss et al found that the presence of cardiac involvement necessitated treatment with corticosteroids combined with immunosuppressive therapy in all cases [14]. Ben Achour et al. reported that corticosteroid therapy (1

mg/kg/day) and immunosuppressive therapy were administered in 71% and 38% of patients respectively [15]. In the study by Harouna and colleagues, the majority of their patients received corticosteroids (94%), synthetic antimalarials (70%) and a converting enzyme inhibitor (12.9%) [17]. As soon as lupus cardiac disease is diagnosed, corticosteroids should be introduced by the treating physician, in combination with cardioprotective treatment. In this study, after the hospital stay, the death rate was 19.1%, or 4 cases out of 21. Harouna et al. in 2016 found a favorable outcome in 93.5% of cases [17]. Our study reports a fairly high death rate compared with the literature despite a low prevalence, particularly for cases of pericardial tamponade with 100% in-hospital deaths. Cardiac involvement in lupus is therefore a morbimortality factor for these patients if not detected and treated in time.

CONCLUSION

Systemic lupus erythematosus is an autoimmune disease of as yet unidentified etiology. The disease affects several organs, including the heart. All tunics of the heart, as well as the valves and coronary arteries, can be affected. The aim of the present study is to determine the sociodemographic, clinical and paraclinical profile, as well as the therapeutic profile, of patients presenting with systemic lupus erythematosus with cardiac involvement. In Madagascar, cardiac involvement among lupus sufferers is rare, accounting for 16.1% of cases at the JRB and CENHOSOA teaching hospitals over 7 years. The most affected subjects are young women under thirty. Dyspnea and edema are the most frequent symptoms revealing cardiac involvement. Lupus pericarditis is the most frequent cardiac manifestation, followed by lupus myocarditis and Libman Sacks endocarditis. Lupus heart disease can be diagnosed before, during or after the diagnosis of lupus. The majority of lupus patients have marked anti-nuclear and anti-native DNA antibody positivity. High-dose corticosteroid therapy is always indicated in cardiac disease, with rare recourse to surgery. Mortality in lupus patients with cardiac involvement appears to be fairly high, especially in those diagnosed late. Cardiac involvement must be systematically investigated, even in the absence of clinical signs, as it is life-threatening and necessitates the introduction of an initial treatment based on high-dose corticosteroids and immunosuppressive therapy. Echocardiography is an excellent non-invasive tool for cardiac evaluation. The search for the causes of non-screening, delayed diagnosis and delayed management is an area for further research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

We have no conflicts of interest.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Solohery Jean Noël Ratsimbazafy and Rajo Païdia Radinasoa : Conceptualization; data curation; project administration; writing

All co-authors: investigation; methodology; Data curation; formal analysis; review and editing; software; Visualization

Hanta Marie Danielle Vololontiana: Supervision; validation; visualization.

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